

Assessing Citizen's Trust on Local Government: A Study on Muktagacha and Trishal Upazila

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Abstract

For a long since, local government bodies have provided numerous services to the people. This research aims to assess the citizen's trust in local government institutions, specially the Upazila Parishad. For this, a survey approach is used to obtain primary data from two Upazila in the Mymensingh district: Muktagacha Upazila and Trishal Upazila. This study shows that the Upazila Parishad activities are insufficient to fulfill the needs of the local population. The Upazila Parishad has an extremely low level of public confidence. Unskilled labor, improper planning, and a lack of financial resources are all identified as problems. The authorities also lack professionalism and exhibit poor conduct while on the job. Upazila authorities did not provide the greatest service to the majority of service recipients. However, the findings of this research imply that the service provided by the Upazila Parishad should be enhanced. The quality of service provided by officials should reflect the high standard of training to which they have been held. Achieving the public's confidence requires providing exceptional service. It is also imperative that the government takes extra measures to enhance the Upazila Parishad system.

Keywords: Citizen's Trust, Local Government, Local Government Institutions, Upazila Parishad, Bangladesh.

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1. Introduction

The Upazila Parishad is a vital component of the local government administration. This is responsible for delivering essential services to the people living under the Upazila parishad. The growth of rural and urban regions is equally dependent on it. They are essential to the progress of many fields, including agriculture, medicine, education, infrastructure, and more. They advance the public interest by delivering services efficiently and earning a citizen's confidence. The functions of the Upazila Parishad include addressing administrative and institutional matters, enforcing law and order and providing services relating to the welfare of the people, and formulating and implementing local economic and social development plans (Habib, 2009). In the past few years, government institutions have changed in developing countries because of things like globalization, financial reforms, democratization, and pressure from the private and other sectors to be more involved in making and implementing policy. Government units are expected to build trusting relationships with non-government sectors so they can manage these changes, increase their legitimacy, and improve partnerships that help them carry out public policies more effectively. The Upazila Parishad has almost lost public confidence in respect to provide their citizen centric services. By keeping them dysfunctional, improper planning, and even lack of financial resources are all identified as problems. The official bodies have lack of professionalism and show poor conduct while performing their assigned duties. On top of that Upazilla Parishad has not provided the utmost services to the vast majority of service recipients (Liton, 2011). In this situation, it is said that getting people to trust government organizations is a must for good governance and successful policy implementation. A democratic system that works well is usually built on the trust of its citizens. Without that trust, social cohesion may weaken. So, most people agree that trust is a good way to measure how well the government units and institutions are dealing and managing with the most important problems they face (Khan et al., 2021). When it comes to providing services at the Upazila level, the Upazila s are having some trouble. The community's people need a better understanding of the local government official's roles they must play. The service providers at the Upazila level need to be better-informed about what they do. Citizen does not have an opportunity to participate in the preparation and execution of projects, and political representatives and the local government officials need to have effective collaborative relationships, just to the name of a few several problems. This research examines how Upazilla Parishad, a body of the local government institution, accomplishes the degree of public trust through performing their assigned functions.

2. Objectives of the Study

The general objective is to assess the citizen's trust in local government institutions. To achieve its general objective, it also covers the following special objectives:

- a) To find out how the relationship between government institutions and the citizen's trust have been seriously affected while providing service delivery.
- b) To further know how the officials, work for their own interest in Upazila Parishad instead of focusing citizens benefit.

3. Review of Literature

Mahmud (2017) focused on his study that residents have a high degree of trust in municipal corporations, which suggests a cumulative pattern as the key conclusion. A high degree of trust regarding one measure has the tendency to spread to others. In Bangladesh, social and cultural determinants possess a more significant impact than institutional or performance variables on variations in residents' trust in local governments. Demographic variables, most notably the occupations of residents are also influenced Trust in the municipality. The quality of service provided by officials should reflect the high standard of training to which they have been held. Achieving the citizen's confidence requires providing exceptional service. It is also imperative that the government take extra measures to enhance the Upazila Parishad system. Yasmin et al. (2017) investigate the inter relationship between perceived accountability of Upazila Parishad and citizen trust in Bangladesh. The authors used a survey method and found that perceived accountability positively influences citizen trust in Upazila Parishad. The study suggests that increasing transparency and accountability in local government can enhance citizen trust. Citizen's satisfaction with the services provided by Upazila Parishad is closely linked to their trust in the Upazila Parishad.

A study conducted by Hasan and Hasan (2018) found that found that transparency, accountability, responsiveness, and participation are the key factors influencing citizen trust in Upazila Parishad. Trust in Upazila Parishad increases if they are satisfied with the services provided, such as infrastructure, development, education, health, and sanitation. Moreover, the study found that the perception of corruption also influences the citizen's trust in Upazila Parishad. Mahmud (2021) narrated that the level of trust citizens has in public institutions is a critical measure of effective governance. In addition, the study focused on citizens' trust in local administrative institutions, specifically the Upazila administrative offices in Bangladesh, and aim to identify the factors that contribute to variations in trust levels. Furthermore, it has been observed that civic engagement and associations established to secure service have a stronger influence on trust levels in Upazila administrative offices than performance-related variables. (Khan et al., 2021) interrogated the people's faith in Upazila Parishad, a historically prominent type of local government organization in

Bangladesh. According to the investigation, the majority of citizens are dissatisfied with the performance of Upazila Parishad. This lower degree of trust proved attributable to problems like service delivery backlogs, fraudulent and unfair practices, and inappropriate behavior on behalf of service providers. Providers of services highlighted several 'supply-side' obstacles to good performance, such as the difficulty of fulfilling a demand that is increasing along with insufficient resources, employee turnover, limited opportunities for training on modern technology, and pressures and influence from solid elites.

Akter et al., (2020) in their study delineated that how men are more culturally aware of local organizations. He also said that education is the factor that might affect the level of trust. The study demonstrates that respondents' financial level may influence their trust level. Citizens with higher incomes in rural areas generally obtain timely and high-quality services, which has a significant impact on their level of trust. The workforce is more knowledgeable than the unemployed. The ineffectiveness of the local development program is partly due to a lack of funding and inexperienced administration. In addition, financial allocations declared in public sessions were not executed promptly, according to the study. Due to the lack of competent workers, fiscal constraints, and other issues, the Upazila cannot undertake these programs. The majority of respondents were eventually dissatisfied with the Upazila Parishad's entire performance in local development. The Upazila Parishad has an extremely low level of public confidence. Unskilled labor, improper planning with no preparation, and a scarcity of financial resources are all identified as problems. The authorities also lack professionalism and exhibit poor conduct while on the job. Upazila authorities did not provide the greatest service to the vast majority of service recipients.

However, Naz (2020) discussed how the relation was badly affected between the citizen and the government during the corona pandemic. The citizens saw how the government failed to keep its trust regarding the proper service to the people. Ultimately, this lack of confidence hampered efforts to contain the pandemic. After a preceding literature review, it can be summarized that many articles have been discussed regarding the citizen's trust in local government institutions. A few studies have been discussed regarding the citizens trust in Upazila level. As a result, this will be a great scope to conduct research in this particular area.

4. Materials and Methods

Research Design: The study is descriptive as well as explanatory in nature. The relationship between Upazila Parishad and the trust of the citizen was examined from a regional (rural and urban) perspective. In this research, both qualitative and quantitative research methods have been used.

Sources of Data: This study relies on a combination of primary as well as secondary data sources. We used both data sources to conclude the study. Using a semi-structured questionnaire, in-depth interviews (face-to-face) and observation methods were used to collect primary data for this research and relevant publications, journal articles, books, papers are analyzed to collect secondary data.

The Study Area: Muktagacha Upazila and Trishal Upazila are study areas in the Mymensingh district. The Upazilas from the Mymensingh district are selected through a random process.

Population, Sample and Sampling Method: This study explores the rural and urban relationship between the local government tier (Upazila Parishad) and service seekers trust. We collected primary data from 120 respondents, including official representatives (20) and the general citizens (100) who receive essential services within the two respective Upazila. The Purposive sampling method is being used to get the viewpoint of the people and the officials.

Study areas (Upazila Parishad)	District	Respondents Selection Criteria	Type of Research Methods	Number of Respondents
Muktagacha	Mymensingh	Elected representatives, and designated government officials.	Key Informant Interviews (KIIs)	2*10 = 20
Trishal		The General citizens.	Questionnaire Survey	2*50 = 100

Table 1: Sampling.

5. Theoretical and Analytical Framework

Institutional theory suggests that social norms and values, which are often taken for granted and deeply ingrained in a society's culture, shape organizations and institutions. According to this theory, the legitimacy and effectiveness of an organization depend on how well it conforms to these social norms and values. In the context of local government bodies, institutional theory suggests that citizen's trust in these bodies is based on their perceived legitimacy and effectiveness in addressing community problems and delivering public services. Citizens are more likely to trust local government bodies that are seen as conforming to social norms and values that are important to them, such as fairness, transparency, and accountability. This theory also emphasizes the importance of legitimacy in shaping citizen's trust in local government bodies (Guth, 2016).

Figure 1: Framework of the Institutional Theory.

Analytical Framework

"Citizens' Trust in Upazila Parishad" is the variable that is being looked at. Some of the trust categories, such as institutional trust (transparency, accessibility, and performance), competence trust (competence), and system trust, have been used to come up with independent variables (credibility of commitment).

Figure 2. Analytical Framework.

6. Findings of the Study

We collected primary data from 120 respondents, including official representatives (20) and the general citizens (100) who receive essential services within the two respective Upazila. The data has been gathered through an interview schedule with an utmost formality. The data has been illustrated below:

6.1 Demographic Attributes on Trust

6.1.1 Income and Trust

The respondents' income level may influence the amount of trust. Citizens with greater incomes in remote areas often get efficient and prompt services, which affects their degree of trust in the long term. On the other hand, lower income individuals, they may have less access to the amenities of LGIs, which might impact their confidence level.

Table 2. *Entire Citizen's Trust*

		Number of Respondent	Level of Trust (%)	
			High	Low
Income	0-5000	21	23.81	76.19
	5000-10000	42	30.95	69.05
	10000-30000	33	42.42	57.58
	30000+	24	62.50	37.50
Total Percentage		120	39.17	60.83

Source: Field Survey.

6.1.2 Occupation and Trust

The occupational status of the respondents may affect the level of trust. It is considered that skilled individuals have a greater understanding of the structures of the institutions, functional procedures, and the internal mechanisms of local government institutions. In contrast, individuals who are not employed might have limited knowledge of regulatory processes as well as institutional systems.

Table 3. *Entire Citizen's Trust*

		Respondent (in Number)	Level of Trust (%)	
			High	Low
Occupational Status	Working People	96	57.29	42.71
	Non-working People	24	33.33	66.67
Total Percentage		120	52.50	47.50

Source: Field Survey.

6.2 Institutional Attributes on Trust

6.2.1 Expertness along with Trust

Table 4. *Upazila's Operative Role in Local Development*

Categories of Response	Service Receiver (in Number)	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	78	78.0	78.0
No	22	22.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	

Source: Field Survey.

The above table presented data about Upazila Parishad that can represent a major role in local development. 78% of the citizen who receive services from the respected Upazila agreed with the statement that there is effective role in local government and 22% of the respondents did not agree with this.

Table 5. *The Effectiveness regarding Local Development Program in Upazila*

Categories of Response	Officials (in Number)	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	12	60.0	60.0
No	4	20.0	80.0
Neutral	4	20.0	100.0
Total	20	100.0	

Source: Field Survey.

The above table presented that 60% of the officials responded with a positive answer and stated that the development programs which are beneficial for the citizen of rural areas of Upazila Parishad was fruitful in their area. On the other hand, 20% of the officials disagreed, and 20% did not respond to this issue of the effectiveness of the local development program in Upazila Parishad. The level of faith that citizens have in the actions of the Upazila Parishad is low. Citizens, in general, hold unfavorable preconceptions of the functionaries of the Upazila Parishad.

Table 6. *Knowledge regarding Responsibility of the Officials*

Categories of Response	Service Receiver (in Number)	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	16	16.0	16.0
Agree	13	13.0	29.0
Neutral	7	7.0	36.0
Disagree	34	34.0	70.0

Strongly Disagree	30	30.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	

Source: Field Survey.

From the primary data collection, we found that 64% of respondents firmly opposed that officials have adequate knowledge of their roles and responsibilities. Often, the officials were not well enough professional with the service delivery process and their behavior remained unfriendly. They remained busy to get their personal interest. The officials sometimes create an unwanted and bad situation in office due to poor knowledge in selective activity with proper guidance. On the other hand, 13% of the respondents agreed with the statement and 7% remained neutral.

6.3 Accessibility and Trust

Table 7. *Access to Citizen in the Budget Making Procedure*

Categories of Response	Officials (in Number)	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	10	50.0	50.0
Agree	6	30.0	80.0
Neutral	4	20.0	100.0
Total	20	100.0	

Source: Field Survey.

80% of the Upazila Parishad officials stated that general people have access to the budget making process in Upazila Parishad. In the open meeting general people can make opinions and also in the standing committees regarding fiscal budget.

6.4 Credibility of Commitment and Trust

Table 8. *Fulfilling Election Mandate by UZP Representatives*

Categories of Response	Service Receiver (in Number)	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	36	36.0	36.0
No	64	64.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	

Source: Field Survey.

With 64% of respondents saying no, the table demonstrated that most Upazila representatives of local government institutions failed to fulfill their mandate to do. Most of the time, the officials seemed busy doing things that helped to get their benefit. On the other hand, 64% of the respondents who answered this question agreed with this.

Table 9. *Allocated Budget Implementation in Open Meeting*

Categories of Response	Service Receiver (in Number)	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	8	8.0	8.0
Agree	10	10.0	18.0
Neutral	12	12.0	30.0
Disagree	24	24.0	54.0
Strongly Disagree	46	46.0	100.0
Total	100		

Source: Field Survey.

70% of the respondents stated that the open meeting budgets were not properly executed through the participation of the general public, as Upazila could not implement these programs due to the shortage of skilled people and fiscal problems.

6.5 Helpfulness and Trust

Table 10. *Helpful Minded Officials*

Categories of Response	Service Receiver (in Number)	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	21	21.0	21.0
Agree	7	7.0	28.0
Neutral	19	19.0	47.0
Disagree	29	29.0	76.0
Strongly Disagree	24	24.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	

Source: Field Survey.

The above table stated that 53% of the respondents disagreed with the opinion that the officials were helpful minded to deliver proper services to the citizen, whereas 28% agreed with a positive response in this matter and 19% of the respondents remained neutral regarding this matter.

Table 11. *Level of Professionalism of Officials*

Categories of Response	Officials (in Number)	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	10	50.0	50.0
Agree	6	30.0	80.0
Neutral	4	20.0	100.0
Total	20	100.0	

Source: Field Survey.

80% of the Upazila Parishad officials confessed that the officials are quite professional while in acting their duties and selective activities. On the other hand, 20% of the officials did not respond regarding this statement. Citizens, in general, hold unfavorable preconceptions of the functionaries of the Upazila Parishad. The Upazila Parishad has a bad reputation for lack of professionalism in service delivery among the people.

6.6 Engagement and trust of the citizen on Upazila Parishad

Table 12. *The Engagement of Citizen in local government activities*

Categories of Response	Service Receiver (in Number)	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	9	9.0	9.0
Agree	8	8.0	17.0
Neutral	25	25.0	42.0
Disagree	38	38.0	80.0
Strongly Disagree	20.	20.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	

Source: Field Survey.

The above table represented that 58% of the respondents disagreed with the matter that people’s participation in a local government program could be possible. Citizens, in general, hold unfavorable preconceptions of the functionaries of the Upazila Parishad. Upazila Parishad officials have a bad reputation for its neglect perception to make participation of citizens in a local government development program, whereas 17% of the respondents agreed with the matter and 25% of the respondents were neutral regarding this statement.

6.7 Trust of Citizen on Upazila Parishad Officials

Table 13. *Trust on Upazila Elected and Non-Elected Officials*

Categories of Response	No. of Service Receiver	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Lowest Level	35	35.0	25.0
Quite Low Level	20	20.0	58.3
Average Level	29	29.0	73.3
Quite High Level	13	13.0	95.0
High Level	3	3.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	

Source: Field Survey.

The above table pointed out that 55% of the respondents had less trust on the officials who are elected and non – elected of Upazila Parishad, whereas 16% of the respondents have a considerable degree of trust and 29% of the respondents have an average level of trust on the officials.

6.8 Entire Performance of Upazila

Table 14. *Entire Performance of Upazila in Local Development*

Categories of Response	Service Receiver (in Number)	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Highly Dissatisfied	21	21.0	21.0
Dissatisfied	33	33.0	54.0
Neutral	19	19.0	73.0
Satisfied	11	11.0	84.0
Highly Satisfied	16	16.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	

Source: Field Survey.

A majority of the survey respondents, precisely 54%, expressed dissatisfaction with the entire performance of the Upazila Parishad in terms of local development. A proportion of 19% of the participants refrained from answering the mentioned issue. The rest of 28.3% of the respondents expressed satisfaction with the entire performance in terms of local development.

7. Discussion of the Study

Upazila Parishad is the second lowest tier of local government in Bangladesh, responsible for providing public services and implementing development programs at the root level. However, despite its significant role in local governance, the citizens' trust in Upazila Parishad activities is generally low.

It is found that, citizens with a high range of income (30000 to above) in Muktagacha and Trishal Upazilla have 62.50% trust on LGIs because they get prompt and quality services. On the contrary, individuals who have a lower range of income (below 5000) have 23.81% trust level on LGIs as they do not get required services as per expectation. Similarly, the occupational status of the citizens affects the level of trust in getting services from LGIs. It is seen from the field study that those who are working people have greater level of trust as they have a good understanding with the officials of LGIs. And the percentage belongs to 57.29%. On the other hand, those who are non-working citizen, they have to face many difficulties to get required services from the LGIs. For this, they have low level of trust on the officials of LGIs and the figure is 24%.

In general, citizens have a negative view on Upazilla Parshad Functionaries. They believe that there's need to play a vital role of Upazila Parishad in the effective development of local government. Based on field study, 78% of the service receiver claims that Upazila Parishad can be an important tier to take part a major role to provide services effectively for the development of local government. However, it is unfortunate that most of the officials at Upazila Parishad have a little official knowledge. Even, 30% of the service receiver strongly believe, the maximum officials are not professional, and not competent of performing their assigned duties. On the contrary, 60% of the official's states that the two mentioned Upazila are effective in the local development.

In an election mandate, the representatives of Upazila Parishad commit to serving the interest of the people within the local administrative area. In reality, the scenario is totally different. More than fifty percent of the response from the service recipient found to be negative. They claim that the election mandate was not fulfilled at all, even the representatives remain busy to pursue their own benefits. In addition, most of the service recipient said that the declaration of budget allocation in open meetings were not executed properly. But, 80% officials claim that people have great access to open budgeting and also have the role to counter against any wrong issue.

Service receivers, with a number of 53% believe that officials do not have the helping mentality to provide appropriate services. People, in general, have unfavorable notions of officials of the Upazila Parishad, and 58% of them disagree that it is impossible for citizens to participate in programs run by the local government. In addition, citizens have a lower degree of trust in both elected and non-elected representatives in their respective activities.

In terms of the development of the local community, 54% of the service receiver is dissatisfied with the overall performance of the Upazila Parishad.

Based on the study, the service provided by the Upazila Parishad is not meeting the citizen's expectations and is insufficient in ensuring effectiveness and building trust. The inadequate level of satisfaction is also reflected in the entire performance of the Upazila Parishad, which is deemed unsatisfactory. Furthermore, the respondents have reported unpleasant incidents associated with the functionaries of Upazila, which could be contributing to the lack of trust in the institution.

8. Conclusion

Upazila serves as a link between the local and national government. And as a tier of local government, it plays a vital and effective role in rural and local areas. Recently, the administration of the Upazila has been brought under the supervision of democratically elected representatives. Not only elected representatives, but also bureaucrats are integral components of the Upazila administration's governing system and policy making process. In the past few years, government institutions have changed in developing countries because of things like globalization, financial reforms, democratization, and pressure from the private and other sectors to be more involved in making and implementing policy. Government units are expected to build trusting relationships with non-government sectors so they can manage these changes, increase their legitimacy, and improve partnerships that help them carry out public policies more effectively. The level of faith that citizens have in the actions of the Upazila Parishad is low. Citizens, in general, hold unfavorable preconceptions of the functionaries of the Upazila Parishad. The Upazila Parishad has a bad reputation for its inefficiency in service delivery among the people.

However, not only elected representatives, but also non-elected officials are often unprofessional in their jobs. Generally, they do not provide essential and optimal services in accordance with the needs of the general public. Even elected officials do not meet the needs of the common masses. They do not prioritize the interests of the people. They are engaged in their own pursuits. These are the reasons why citizens have little faith in Upazila authorities. The method of communication and cooperation between the two sets of people, elected representatives and bureaucrats, determines the efficiency of Upazila 's service delivery. The duties and responsibilities of Upazila Parishad are a source of intense debate. The quality of service provided by officials should reflect the high standard of training to which they have been held. Achieving the public's confidence requires providing exceptional service. It is also imperative that the government should take extra measures to enhance the Upazila Parishad system. An important lesson may be drawn from this study is that without the government- citizen well-tuned collaboration, overall trust of the citizens couldn't be ensured.

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